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THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF ETHNOMATHEMATICS TO MATHEMATICS LEARNING IN HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses the contributions of ethnomathematics to the contextualization of mathematical content in secondary education. It examines ethnomathematics and its contributions to the teaching and learning of mathematics. The objective is to analyze the relevance of ethnomathematics and its impact on mathematics learning in secondary education, seeking to provide an educational practice based on concrete situations. The theoretical framework emphasizes the importance of contextualizing mathematical content in secondary education for learning, highlighting the fundamental role of ethnomathematics in achieving this. Pedagogical experiences are reported that demonstrate that the inclusion of ethnomathematical activities in the curriculum contributes to greater student motivation and better performance in mathematics assessments.

Keywords: Ethnomathematics. High School. Mathematics Learning. Contextualization of content.